

Chemical Examination of *Milletia pendula* and *Ficus benjamina* (Fruits)

P. I. Ahmad, S. A. Ahmad and Asif Zaman

Milletia pendula is found in Dehra Dun region. The plant is reported to have toxic properties. No work has been reported on this particular species.

Air dried leaves of the plant (5 kg) were extracted with petroleum ether (60–80°), the extract was concentrated and chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with petrol-benzene (1 : 2) afforded β -sitosterol, m.p. and mixed m.p. 137–38°; acetyl derivative m.p. and mixed m.p. 126–27°.

Ficus benjamina is found in hilly area ascending upto 3,000 ft. Its milky juice is used against whitening of the cornea and leaves mixed with oil applied to ulcers.

Powdered air dried fruits (1 kg) extracted with hot petroleum ether (60–80°), the extract concentrated and chromatographed over alumina. Elution with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 5) yielded bergapten, m.p. and mixed m.p. 189–91°.

Authors are thankful to the Ministry of Health and Family Planning, Government of India for financial assistance.

Department of Research in Unani Medicine,
A. K. Tibbiya College,
Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligarh.

Received May 15, 1971

1. R. N. Chopra, S. L. Nayar and I. C. Chopra, Glossary of Indian medicinal plants, CSIR, New Delhi. 1956, 198.
2. Wealth of India, Vol. IV, 376,

